

HYDROGEOLOGICAL RESEARCH FOR POST-MINING OF THE KIZEL COAL BASIN (THE URALS, RUSSIA)

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ABSTRACT: Coal mining in the Kizel coal basin (the Urals, Russia) was accompanied by intensive mine drainage of both coal seams and hydraulically connected fractured karst aquifers, the formation of extensive depression cones, the displacement of large masses of rocks, the formation of sinkholes. These processes have led to significant changes in the properties of aquifers and groundwater recharge-discharge conditions. After the cessation of drainage, 19 effluents of acid mine waters were formed. To select engineering measures aimed at improving the environmental situation, it was necessary to assess the components of the balance involved in the formation of these effluents. Groundwater in the Kizel coal basin is formed within several relatively isolated catchments. Analysis of the geological, tectonic structure of the territory, conductivity properties of rocks, the geomorphological position of the basin were used to determine the external boundaries of the models. The eight were developed on the basis of long-term data from routine observations during the development of coal mines, generalization of geological and hydrogeological information. For each of the models, the external and internal boundary conditions are determined, stratification is carried out and the main parameters are justified. The analysis was used to justify measures to reduce the discharge of acid mine waters.

Key words: acid mine waters, water balance, models of groundwater flow

HYDROGEOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF THE KIZEL COAL BASIN

The geological section of the Kizel coal basin is represented by sedimentary deposits from the Lower Devonian to the Lower Permian. The coal content is associated with the lower section of the carboniferous system, represented by the Tournaisian, Viseian and Serpukhov tiers (Fig. 1). The total thickness of carbonate deposits in the roof of the coal-bearing strata exceeds 1000 m. The thickness of the coal-bearing strata varies from 150 m within the Main Kizel anticline to 200 m at the Gremyachinsk field.

Fig. 1. Geological map of the Kosva river area [Shcherbakov et al. 1989]. Rocks: 1 - carbonate; 2 - carbonate-sandy-clay; 3 - sandy-clay; 4 - sandy-clay with powerful conglomerates; 5 - stratigraphic breaks; 6 - discontinuous disturbances: a - thrusts on the map, b - thrusts on the profile section, c - upsurges on the map and section; 7 - overhangs: I - Vsevolod-Vilvensky, II - Lunyevsko-Chusovskaya, III — Kosva; overhangs: IV - Maltsevsk and V - Kosogorsk; 8 - sections (1 - Cold Log, 2 - White Mountain).

The main folded structures are the Main Kizel and Gorelov anticlines, Kospash-Poludennaya, Kosogorsk, Kosva, Usva, Nagornninsk, Shumikha, Gremyachaya, Skalninsk, synclines. Folded structures are complicated by numerous discontinuous faults, which have an amplitude from several hundred meters to 1.5 km and can be traced for tens of kilometers. The main discontinuous faults and folded structures have a submeridional strike.

In the hydrogeological section, the following aquifer complexes are distinguished: Viseian-Arta carbonate (C1v3+s-P1a); coal-bearing deposits terrigenous (hC1v1+2); Franco-Tournaisian carbonate (D3fr-C1t); Devonian terrigenous (D). The Vise-Arta aquifer complex of fractured karst waters consists of two aquifers: the Moscow-Arta and Vise-Bashkir aquifers. The horizons are separated by a regional water barrier, which is confined to the lower pack of the Moscow tier of the middle carboniferous and is represented by clay limestones, mudstones.

The Visei-Bashkir aquifer is the most abundant. A number of groundwater sources with a flow rate of more than 100 L/s are associated with it in the basin. Taking into account the good quality and large reserves of horizon water, they are widely used for the water supply of settlements in the territory of the coal basin. Fractured karst waters meet the requirements for drinking water to a depth of at least 1 km. The Viseian-Bashkir horizon took part in the flooding of most of the mines in the basin, in many of them it was the main source of mine water formation. The flow of fractured karst waters into the mine workings occurred through man-made cracks formed in the roofing rocks of spent coal seams during their displacement into the worked-out space.

The groundwater levels of the aquifer complex of coal-bearing deposits decreased to the lower limit of mining operations. The groundwater inflow occurred in the preparatory workings and in the worked-out space of the longwalls. The entire overlying pack of coal-bearing deposits was drained through man-made cracks above the spent coal seams. The water content of the complex is generally small, the aquifers included in it are confined to sandstone strata and are separated by layers of mudstones and siltstones, as well as layers and interlayers of coal. Mine water flows in the upper horizons of mines, formed only by groundwater of the coal-bearing stratum, usually did not exceed 150-200 m³/hour. After the flooding of the spent mine fields, a man-made horizon of mine waters was formed as part of the coal-bearing strata.

Fractured formation waters of the coal-bearing strata took part in the flooding of all mines of the Kizel basin, and in most mines - the waters of the Visei-Artinsk complex. The depth of mining varied from 100 m in the mines of the Usva syncline to 1 km in the mines of the Main Kizel anticline and the Kosva syncline (Imaykin et al. 2022). The highest values of total drainage were recorded at the mines of the Main Kizel anticline (up to 5.5 thousand m³/hour), the Kospash-Poludennaya syncline (up to 3 thousand m³/hour). About 1 thousand m³/hour was the drainage at the mines of the Kosva and Gremyachaya synclines [Pyankov et al. 2021].

FRAME OF THE LOCAL GROUNDWATER BASINS OF THE KIZELOVSKY COAL BASIN

The purpose of flow modeling of the Kizel coal basin is to obtain the balance characteristics of local groundwater basins, within which mine outflows (mining stage) and mine water outflows (mine flooding stage) are formed, to justify engineering measures to reduce outflows.

Specialized software products are used for modeling, such as Model Muse (developed by the US Geological Survey, USGS), which is a pre- and postgraphic processor for software codes ModFlow, MT3D, MODPath, etc. (Anderson et al. 2015). These program codes are generally recognized as highly effective modeling tools both in the world and in Russia.

Groundwater in the territory of the Kizel coal basin is formed within several isolated basins of underground runoff (Fig. 2). Internal boundary conditions are determined by the presence of watercourses, in this case, boundary conditions of the III type were set in the corresponding blocks, determining the relationship between the river and the reservoir. For the model of mining conditions, an important internal boundary condition is drainage (boundary condition of the second type) and the depth of its laying (boundary condition of the first type). For the model of flooding conditions at the outlet (outflow) of mine waters, an absolute outlet mark is set (boundary condition of the first type is the absolute mark of the outflow) or the amount of the outflow (boundary of the second type is the outflow rate) (Table 1).

The models under consideration are multi-layered, they include 2 or 3 aquifers and the strata separating them (Table 2).

Table 1. The main characteristics of groundwater flow models

Geofiltration model	External borders		Internal boundaries, flow rate ^b , m ³ /hour		Model area, km ²	Number of calculation blocks ^c
	direction	BC ^a	drainage	spill		
The main Kizel anticline	N, W, E S	II III (K)	4654	350	153	299*124*5
Kospash-Poludennaya syncline	N, W, E, S	II	2958	345	132	272*135*5
The northern part of the Kosva syncline	N, W, E S	II III (K)	909	399	100	176*82*3
Nagornaya syncline	N W, E, S	III (K) II	293	59	78	143*80*3
The southern part of the Kosva syncline	N W, E, S	III (K) II	1099	594	87	169*89*3
Shumikha syncline	N W, E S	III (K) II III (U)	454	12	31	146*55*3
Usva syncline	N, W, E, S	II	624	100	31 ^r	216*167*3
Gremyachaya syncline	N, W, E, S	II	985	684	53	174*133*3

Notes: a boundary conditions: II type - impermeable boundary; III type – river (K – Kosva, U- Usva); b in total; c along the X*Y*Z axes; d along the area of development of the coal-bearing strata.

Fig. 2. Boundaries of groundwater flow models within the Kizel coal basin (MKA – the Main Kizel anticline, KPS – the Kospash- Poludennaya syncline).

Table 2. Values of filtration and capacitive parameters of groundwater flow models (description of layers from top to bottom)

Layer number	Parameters and their range of change			
	conductivity, m/day	transmissivity, m ² /day	hydraulic diffusivity, m ² /day	thickness, m
Undisturbed conditions				
1 – carbonate aquifer	0,12-0,84	24-259	2,69*10 ¹⁶ -0,03*10 ²	0-400
2 – aquitard	1*10 ⁻²	-	-	10
3 – coal aquifer	0,03-0,14	7-38	0,1*10 ² -7,1*10 ³	0-160
Mining and flooding				
1 – carbonate aquifer	0,12-0,84	24-259	2,69*10 ¹⁶ -0,03*10 ²	0-400
2 – aquitard	1*10 ⁻²	-	-	10
3 – coal aquifer, upper part	0,03-0,14	7-38	0,1*10 ² -7,1*10 ³	70
4 – aquitard	1*10 ⁻²	-	-	10
5 – coal aquifer, the lower part, water-conducting zone	0,3-1,4	35-38	0,1*10 ² -7,1*10 ³	80

THE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using modeling for 8 groundwater basins within the Kizel coal basin, an assessment of the balance components for different stages of territory development was performed: (1) natural undisturbed conditions, (2) mining with mine drainage, (3) the current situation with mine water outflows, (4) implementation of engineering measures (Rybnikov et al. 2018).

The resources of the coal-bearing strata provided, on average, about 50% of the mine drainage. A clear dependence of the flow rate of mine water outflows on seasonality and climatic factors has been established. Currently, up to 50% of the outflow is generated due to surface runoff. To confirm this conclusion, a simulation was performed simulating the availability of years of different water content. The organization of interception and diversion of surface runoff by upland ditches is considered as the main water protection measure (Maksimovich et al. 2019).

Modeling of situations reflecting the implementation of engineering activities aimed at reducing the outflows rate of discharge was performed. For the northern part of the Kosvinsky syncline, when organizing a barrage across the mine water discharge zone, the groundwater level above the barrage will increase by 10-15 m, as a result, a new mine water discharge site will be formed approximately 500 m from the adit on the surface.

The organization of water pumping from the carbonate aquifer with a total amount of 1052 m³/hour (i.e. approximately the same as it was during mining) will reduce the outflow by more than two times - up to 187 m³/hour.

To radically stop the outflow of mine waters, it is effective to organize the drainage of coal-bearing rocks located above the outflow site in the area of the Tsentralnaya mine. In this case, when conducting drainage with a flow rate of 771 m³/hour, the average annual discharge value will decrease to 19 m³/hour (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Changes in the balance components of the groundwater flow model (the northern part of the Kosva syncline) at different stages of the life cycle of the mining territory. a – income items b – outcome items. C1v3 - Viseian-Arta carbonate aquifer; hC1- coal-bearing terrigenous aquifer; w - recharge; in/out - leakage in/out C1v3; R - discharge in river; ΣQ (mine) – mine drainage; ΣQ (AMD) – acid mine water drainage; ΣQ (drainage) - withdrawal for engineering activities

CONCLUSION

The mine drainage at the mines of the Kizelovsky coal basin was completed more than 20 years ago. During this period, acid mine waters are discharged to the surface at 19 sites. To assess the balance components that take part in outflows, 8 numerical models of runoff were developed. The total flow rate of the outflows is formed both at the expense of the resources of the coal-bearing complex (in which, in fact, the formation of acidic waters occurs) and as a result of the areal overflow from the carbonate complex. Such replenishment strongly depends on both the specific season and the water content of the period. The main measures to reduce pollution of the hydrosphere should be directed at intercepting resources above the outflows, within the part of the catchment where groundwater is not yet polluted. This will reduce the consumption of polluted waters pouring onto the surface by more than an order of magnitude.

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